

Supplementary Material

Identification of gut microbiome signatures associated with serotonin pathway in tryptophan metabolism in patients undergoing hemodialysis

Supplementary Methods

Metagenomics sequencing and Raw reads quality control

Extracted DNA (about 500 ng) was fragmented to approximately 350 base pairs by the Covaris S2 system (Covaris, Inc., Woburn, MA, USA) and then subjected to library construction with the Illumina DNA Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, CA). Sequencing is performed using an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencer, resulting in paired-end reads of 150 bp in length. On a per-sample basis, read quality control (QC) is performed using the Kneaddata pipeline (<https://github.com/biobakery/kneaddata>), which integrates Trimmomatic [1] for trimming Illumina adaptors and low-quality regions, filtering short reads and Bowtie2 [2] for identifying and removing host contaminations from human hg38 build (or mouse mm10 build) and PhiX genome. Reads with low complexity regions and repeated sequences are identified and filtered by using the Komplexity software (<https://github.com/eclarke/komplexity>) with default settings.

Metagenome assembly and annotation

Metagenome assembly is conducted by using MEGAHIT [3] to assemble QC-passed reads into contigs. As for taxonomy identification, two approaches are employed: (1) read-based taxonomy, which analyses QC-passed reads using Sourmash [4] to estimate relative abundance of taxa based on GTDB taxonomy [5], and (2) contig-based taxonomy, which predicts taxonomy of contigs using MMSeqs2 [6, 7] easy-taxonomy pipeline and estimates abundance by contigs depth, which is derived by the `jgi_summarize_bam_contig_depths` script analysing bowtie2 alignment that maps QC-passed reads onto contigs. The open reading frame (ORF) prediction and functional annotation, including the Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs) family and Enzyme Commission (EC) number assignment, are performed by subjecting contigs into Prokka [8]. ORFs are also analysed to identify corresponding KEGG Orthology (KO) numbers, Carbohydrate Active enZyme (CAZy) family, antibiotics gene, and virulence factor using MMSeqs2 easy-search pipeline. MinPath [9] is used for pathway reconstruction by analysing KO (for KEGG pathway) and EC (for

MetaCyc pathway [10]) profiles of each sample. The abundance of gene families (or categories) is estimated by accumulating ORF depths, which is calculated by the `tpm_table` python script (<https://github.com/EnvGen/toolbox>) based on the number of unique reads mapped on each ORF and presented in units of transcript per million (TPM) [11]. Metagenomics binning is performed by MetaBAT [12] to cluster contigs into genome “bins” [i.e., metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs)]. The quality is assessed, and the taxonomy is identified by CheckM lineage-specific workflow [13]. Additionally, the taxonomy of MAGs is voted using the contig-based taxonomy of binned contigs, which extends the CheckM-predicted taxonomy to further depth in most cases.

Bioinformatics and statistical analysis

Microbial diversity was assessed using alpha diversity indices (Shannon, Simpson) and beta diversity using PERMANOVA with the “`adonis2`” function from the “`vegan`” package [18]. Principal Coordinate Analysis (PCoA) was used for ordination.

To evaluate associations between microbial taxa (metagenomic species, MGS) and metabolite concentrations, we performed linear regression models adjusted for age and sex. To account for multiple comparisons, **false discovery rate (FDR) correction was applied**, and both unadjusted and FDR-adjusted p-values are reported in the main manuscript (Table 2). Only FDR-significant associations were interpreted as robust.

In addition, we used LEfSe (linear discriminant analysis effect size) to identify differentially abundant taxa and gut metabolic modules between high and low metabolite groups. While LEfSe results are presented to aid visualization and exploratory discovery, interpretation was limited to associations validated through adjusted regression models. All plots were generated using “`ggplot2`” [17].

The initial step involved data preparation using the R package “`phyloseq`” [14], where samples were filtered, rare taxa removed, and species-level aggregation was performed. Patients were categorized into high and low metabolite groups using the median concentration for each metabolite. Group comparisons for clinical variables were conducted using t-tests, Wilcoxon rank-sum tests, or chi-square tests via the “`compareGroups`” package [15, 16]

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Supplementary Figures

Identification of gut microbiome signatures associated with serotonin pathway in tryptophan metabolism in patients undergoing hemodialysis

Supplementary Figure S1. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of 5-HTP Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S2. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of Serotonin Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S3. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of 5-MTP Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S4. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of 5-Methoxytryptamine Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S5. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of Melatonin Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S6. Relative Abundance of Various Genera and Species at Different Levels of 6-Hydroxymelatonin Metabolite from the Serotonin Pathway.

Supplementary Figure S7. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with Serotonin.

(A)

Serotonin (nM)

High
Low

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|---|-------------------------------------|
| a: f__Odoribacteraceae | r: s__Bacteroides xylanisolvens | ai: s__Bacteroides sp. 519 |
| b: f__Dysgonomonadaceae | s: s__Bacteroides caccae | aj: s__Bacteroides sp. CAG:189 |
| c: f__Comamonadaceae | t: s__Bacteroides finegoldii | ak: s__Bacteroides congongensis |
| d: f__Helicobacteraceae | u: s__Bacteroides stercoris CAG:120 | al: s__Bacteroides fragilis CAG:558 |
| e: f__Weeksellaceae | v: s__Anaerotignum lactatifermentans | am: s__Clostridiaceae Family |
| f: f__Rhizobiaceae | w: s__Bacteroides neonati | an: s__Sutterellaceae Family |
| g: f__Alcaligenaceae | x: s__Butyricimonas paravirosa | ao: s__Dorea Genus |
| h: g__Anaerotignum | y: s__Desulfovibrio desulfuricans | ap: s__Prevotella sp. CAG:520 |
| i: g__Dysgonomonas | z: s__Parabacteroides johnsonii CAG:246 | aq: s__Elizabethkingia sp. ASV34 |
| j: g__Delftia | aa: s__Parabacteroides goldsteinii | ar: s__Azospirillum sp. 51_20 |
| k: g__Helicobacter | ab: s__Alistipes sp. D311f_170403_E11 | as: s__[Clostridium] symbiosum |
| l: g__Clostridiaceae Family | ac: s__Bacteroides sp. CAG:633 | at: s__Achromobacter sp. ASV32 |
| m: g__Sutterellaceae Family | ad: s__Bacteroides sp. AM16-15 | au: s__Rhizobium sp. ASV8 |
| n: g__Lachnoclostridium | ae: s__Delftia sp. ASV31 | av: s__Clostridium disporicum |
| o: g__Elizabethkingia | af: s__Alistipes shahii | aw: s__Prevotella intermedia |
| p: g__Achromobacter | ag: s__Helicobacter felis | ax: s__Eubacterium sp. CAG:180 |
| q: g__Rhizobium | ah: s__Bacteroides sp. HPS0048 | |

(B)

Supplementary Figure S8. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with 5-HTP.

(A)

(B)

Supplementary Figure S9. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of 5-HTP.

Supplementary Figure S10. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of 5-HTP.

Supplementary Figure S11. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of Serotonin.

Supplementary Figure S12. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of Serotonin.

Supplementary Figure S13. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with 5-MTP.

(A)

(B)

5-MTP (nM)

■ High
■ Low

- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| ■ a: f__Oscillospiraceae | ■ u: s__Desulfovibrio piger | ■ ao: s__Ruminococcus bromii |
| ■ b: f__Eubacteriaceae | ■ v: s__Eubacterium sp. CAG:38 | ■ ap: s__Ruminococcaceae bacterium TF06-43 |
| ■ c: f__Barnesiellaceae | ■ w: s__Oscillibacter sp. | ■ aq: s__Ruminococcus sp. |
| ■ d: f__Candidatus Borkfalkiaceae | ■ x: s__Anaerotruncus Genus | ■ ar: s__Coproccoccus fastidiosus |
| ■ e: g__Oscillospiraceae Family | ■ y: s__Prevotella sp. | ■ as: s__Alistipes onderdonkii |
| ■ f: g__Ruminococcus | ■ z: s__Clostridium sp. CAG:273 | ■ at: s__Prevotella sp. CAG:1320 |
| ■ g: g__Eubacterium | ■ aa: s__Merdimonas faecis | ■ au: s__Anaerotruncus massiliensis |
| ■ h: g__Rikenellaceae Family | ■ ab: s__Clostridium sp. CAG:169 | ■ av: s__Monoglobus pectiniilyticus |
| ■ i: g__Merdimonas | ■ ac: s__Prevotella sp. CAG:1092 | ■ aw: s__Faecalibacterium sp. CAG:74_58_120 |
| ■ j: g__Anaerofilium | ■ ad: s__Clostridium sp. CAG:242 | ■ ax: s__Clostridium sp. 27_14 |
| ■ k: g__Coproccoccus | ■ ae: s__Eubacterium sp. OM08-24 | ■ ay: s__Bacteroides ovatus |
| ■ l: g__Barnesiella | ■ af: s__Roseburia intestinalis | ■ az: s__[Ruminococcus] gnavus |
| ■ m: g__Parasutterella | ■ ag: s__[Eubacterium] rectale | ■ ba: s__Clostridium sp. CAG:440 |
| ■ n: g__Monoglobus | ■ ah: s__Blautia hansenii | ■ bb: s__Bacteroides sp. CAG:754 |
| ■ o: g__Porphyromonadaceae Family | ■ ai: s__uncultured Faecalibacterium sp. | ■ bc: s__Clostridium sp. CAG:571 |
| ■ p: g__Candidatus Borkfalkia | ■ aj: s__Ruminococcus sp. CAG:579 | ■ bd: s__Porphyromonadaceae bacterium |
| ■ q: s__Oscillospiraceae Family | ■ ak: s__Coproccoccus comes | ■ be: s__Candidatus Borkfalkia ceftriaxoniphila |
| ■ r: s__Ruminococcus Genus | ■ al: s__Butyricimonas virosa | ■ bf: s__Ruminococcus sp. Marseille-P6503 |
| ■ s: s__Oscillospiraceae bacterium | ■ am: s__Barnesiella intestinihominis | ■ bg: s__Erysipelatoclostridium Genus |
| ■ t: s__Rikenellaceae Family | ■ an: s__Prevotella sp. CAG:5226 | |

Supplementary Figure S14. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of 5-MTP.

Supplementary Figure S15. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of 5-MTP.

Supplementary Figure S16. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with 5-Methoxytryptamine.

(A)

(B)

Supplementary Figure S17. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of 5-Methoxytryptamine.

Supplementary Figure S18. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of 5-Methoxytryptamine.

Supplementary Figure S19. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with Melatonin.

(A)

(B)

Supplementary Figure S20. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of Melatonin

Supplementary Figure S21. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of Melatonin.

Supplementary Figure S22. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis and Cladogram Construction for the Microbiome Associated with 6-Hydroxymelatonin.

(A)

(B)

Supplementary Figure S23. The Comparison of Standardized Relative Abundance Between High and Low Levels of 6-Hydroxymelatonin

Supplementary Figure S24. LEfSe (Linear Discriminant Analysis Effect Size) Analysis of Gut Metabolic Modules Based on the Level of 6-Hydroxymelatonin.

